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**19th International Conference
on Chemistry and the Environment**
Belgrade, Serbia, June 8-12, 2025

Environmental Chemistry for Sustainability

E-Book of Abstracts

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Dear participants, welcome to Belgrade!

On behalf of the Division of Chemistry and the Environment (DCE) (<https://www.euchems.eu/divisions/chemistry-and-the-environment-2/>) of the European Association of the Chemical Societies (EuChemS) (<https://www.euchems.eu/>), the Serbian Chemical Society (<https://www.shd.org.rs/en/>), and the local organizing committee, it is our great pleasure and privilege to warmly welcome you to the 19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE 2025).

This prestigious event, which gathers nearly 350 participants from across the globe is hosted by the Serbian Chemical Society with the support of the University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad.

At a time when continued scientific progress is essential to ensure a healthy environment and a sustainable future, ICCE 2025 addresses key challenges and emerging developments, advances knowledge and inspires action through the lens of Environmental Chemistry. In addition to the main program running in fourteen parallel sessions, ICCE 2025 will feature four pre-conference satellite events, each dedicated to current research priorities and strategic environmental topics and EuChemS DCE Career Award lecture by Terry Frank Bidleman from Sweden. The scientific program includes seven plenary lectures including two Distinguished Lectures from the American Chemical Society, and fourteen keynote lectures that introduce parallel sessions, comprising 175 oral and 156 poster presentations. A Special Editorial Panel Discussion, with editors from leading international scientific journals, will provide valuable insight into the evolving landscape of scientific publishing.

ICCE 2025 provides an excellent platform for networking, exchange of ideas and collaboration. Our collective mission is to deepen understanding of pollutant's cycling, and their fate and effects in the environment, while advancing pollution prevention and waste management. The latest developments in environmental analysis, pollution monitoring and risk assessment directly impact societal response to environmental challenges, which inevitably focus on various sustainability strategies. To be effective, these responses must be supported by excellent knowledge-based tools and societal inspiration, both offered by ICCE 2025.

We hope that you will not only enjoy the rich scientific program but also take-home memorable experiences from Serbia!

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Special thanks to the Evertéa Foundation, which generously provided registration grants to a number of students and early-career researchers from around the world who would otherwise not have had the opportunity to attend. Additionally, the best oral and poster presentations will be recognized and awarded by the Local Organizing Committee, with Springer eBook vouchers as prizes.

Roland Kallenborn, EuChemS DCE Chairman, Antonio Marcomini, previous ICCE 2023 Chairman and Philippe Garrigues, Editor-in-Chief of *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* provided us with valuable guidance in shaping the format and structure of this year's conference in line with the ICCE tradition. The input of all EuChemS DCE members was instrumental in refining the scientific program, selecting invited speakers, and ensuring a robust and fair abstract review process. We deeply appreciate the support of our colleagues from partner associations as George Cobb, John Giesy and Virender Kumar Sharma from Division on Environmental Chemistry of the American Chemical Society (ACSEnv), Roberto Terzano, Hemda Garelick and Melanie Kah from International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) and Takeshi Nakano from Japan Society for Environmental Chemistry for helping us to make this event remarkable.

Company "Congrexpo" d.o.o., our professional conference organizer, led by Mrs. Olivera Popović, manages all logistics and technical coordination with dedication and professionalism. The Hotel M team, under the direction of Mrs. Jelena Jakovljević, ensures a welcoming and pleasant experience for all participants in the warm and familiar setting of one of Belgrade's most established congress venues. A very special "thank you" goes to our volunteers Slaven Tenodi, Tijana Marijanović, Sanja Vasiljević, Dušan Rakić, Marija Simić, Katarina Stojanović, Marija Kovačević, Ana Lazić, and Lazar Popović.

We thank all the participants for their oral and poster presentations which make the ICCE2025 shining!

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Phosphorus extraction from sewage sludge ash

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Phosphate rock, the primary source of phosphorus, is a non-renewable resource, and its depletion raises concerns about future phosphorus availability. Additionally, phosphate-based fertilizers exhibit low efficiency, with approximately 80% of the applied phosphorus remaining unused, contributing to eutrophication in aquatic ecosystems. As a result, the recovery of phosphorus from alternative sources has gained increasing importance in recent years. One promising secondary phosphorus source is incinerated sewage sludge ash (ISSA), a byproduct of wastewater treatment plant sludge mono-incineration. However, effective extraction techniques are necessary to separate phosphorus from contaminants and enable its reuse. Among various approaches, wet chemical extraction using organic acids has been recognized as an efficient method. This study investigates the potential of phosphorus extraction from ISSA using oxalic acid, focusing on the influence of extraction time and acid concentration on the efficiency of the process. The sludge sample analyzed in this study contained approximately 22% dry matter, whereas the moisture content in the ISSA sample was low (0.5%).

Figure 3 The influence of oxalic acid concentration on the efficiency of phosphorus extraction over a duration of 240 minutes

The total phosphorus content in ISSA was determined to be 160.55 mg/g, indicating its potential as a viable phosphorus source. All extractions were performed at a constant liquid-to-solid (L/S) ratio of 20:1. The results showed that phosphorus extraction efficiency exceeded 50% in all cases. However, due to the incineration process at 850°C, sintering and melting of iron and silicon particles present in the ash could occur. This phenomenon may reduce the permeability of the acid within the ash pores, limiting its interaction with phosphorus-containing compounds and slightly lowering extraction efficiency compared to expected values [1, 2]. To achieve an extraction efficiency above 80%, an extraction time of 240 minutes was required. For this duration, the dependence of phosphorus extraction efficiency on oxalic acid concentration was analyzed. The highest extraction efficiency (96.05%) was achieved at an oxalic acid concentration of 0.2 mol/dm³. These findings demonstrate that oxalic acid is an effective reagent for phosphorus recovery from ISSA, with extraction time and acid concentration playing a crucial role in process optimization. This study contributes to the advancement of sustainable phosphorus recovery strategies, reducing reliance on finite phosphate rock reserves while mitigating environmental issues related to phosphorus loss and eutrophication.

Acknowledgments

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References

- [1] Li, J. S. et al. (2020) Phosphorus (P) recovery and reuse as fertilizer from incinerated sewage sludge ash (ISSA), *Current Developments in Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 263-288.
- [2] Liang, S. et al. (2021) Phosphorus recovery from incinerated sewage sludge ash (ISSA) and reutilization of residues for sludge pretreated by different conditioners, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 169, 105524.

Electrochemical treatments in the circular economy: Innovative approaches to wastewater management and resource recovery

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Integrating circular economy principles into wastewater treatment enables resource recovery and reuse, transforming sanitation from a cost-intensive service into a self-sustaining system that generates value. This paper presents the results of research conducted under the Horizon Europe project "Wastewater Management in Circular Economy Frame (SmartWaterTwin)," which represents Serbia's first step in wastewater management within the framework of the circular economy. It is crucial to recognize the true value of wastewater and the potential resources that can be recovered from it. One of the research focuses is on electrochemical treatments as innovative wastewater treatment technologies and the recovery of valuable materials (water, phosphorus, and nitrogen) from wastewater.

The study by Leovac Maćerak et al. (2024) [1] demonstrated that the bipolar electrode arrangement Al(-)/Al/Al/Al(+) effectively removes pollutants from municipal wastewater in accordance with national regulations, while LCA analysis highlights the need for using renewable energy sources and more environmentally friendly electrode materials. Additionally, the research by Duduković et al. (2024) [2] confirmed that treated wastewater, following bipolar electrocoagulation, can be a valuable resource for agricultural irrigation, meeting both national and international quality standards.

One promising method for nutrient recovery is the electrochemical precipitation of struvite, a sustainable slow-release fertilizer. Duduković et al. (2024) [3] investigated the electrochemical precipitation of phosphorus using a synthetic sample of anaerobic digester supernatant, achieving complete P removal at pH levels of 7.5–10, while nitrogen content decreased with increasing pH. XRD analysis confirmed the presence of struvite in the precipitates, highlighting the potential of this method for sustainable nutrient management in wastewater treatment.

Adopting a circular economy approach in wastewater treatment enables the recovery of valuable resources and reduces the environmental footprint. Electrochemical treatments, particularly electrocoagulation and electrochemical struvite precipitation, have proven to be effective and sustainable solutions for nutrient recycling and water reuse.

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References

- [1] Leovac Maćerak, A. et al. (2024) Electrocoagulation in treatment of municipal wastewater– life cycle impact assessment. *Chemosphere*, 355, 141701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2024.141701>
- [2] Duduković, N. et al. (2024) Treated municipal wastewater – a potential resource in agriculture. 53rd Conference – Waste Waters, Municipal Solid Wastes and Hazardous Wastes, Kragujevac, Serbia
- [3] Duduković, N. et al. (2024) Electrochemical precipitation potential for recovering phosphorous. 9th Regional Symposium on Electrochemistry, South-East Europe, Novi Sad, Serbia June 3-7 2024.

A circular economy approach to wastewater management: A toolkit for sustainable resource recovery and reuse

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For the implementing circular economy principles into wastewater sector, it is necessary to develop comprehensive approach. Particularly in developing countries, the toolkit form provides practical strategies, capacity-building frameworks and proposed financial models to overcome infrastructure and regulatory challenges, facilitating the transition to resource recovery while supporting climate resilience and long-term sustainability. The SmartWater Toolkit is designed to facilitate the integration of circular economy principles in the wastewater sector, offering a strategic approach for optimizing water reuse, nutrient recovery, and energy generation. This toolkit provides technical, policy, and infrastructural guidance to transform wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) into resource-efficient systems, particularly in developing countries. The toolkit encompasses several critical areas:

Regulatory frameworks and policy alignment – It reviews European policies such as the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, and national regulations in Republic of Serbia to provide a roadmap for policy harmonization in developing economies. The toolkit offers recommendations for implementing effective governance, investment strategies, and legislative frameworks to support circular wastewater management.

Best practices and case studies – Drawing from successful circular economy initiatives in Europe and Republic of Serbia, the document presents real-world applications of water reuse, biogas production, and nutrient recovery. These case studies offer replicable models for developing countries seeking to transition from conventional wastewater treatment to resource recovery-oriented systems.

Technological innovations for resource recovery – The toolkit highlights key technologies for sustainable wastewater management, including; Water reuse technologies – Advanced filtration, disinfection, and quality control measures to ensure treated wastewater meets agricultural and industrial standards; Nutrient recovery – Phosphorus and nitrogen extraction methods such as struvite precipitation and composting for agricultural use; Energy generation from wastewater – Biogas recovery through anaerobic digestion, cogeneration systems, and sludge-to-energy pathways to enhance energy self-sufficiency in WWTPs.

Sludge management and agricultural application – Given that sludge reuse is a cost-effective and environmentally beneficial practice, the toolkit provides a methodology for safe sludge application in agriculture, following EU standards. It includes guidelines on sludge treatment, storage, transport, and quality assessment to mitigate environmental and health risks.

Stakeholder engagement and capacity building – Successful circular economy implementation requires collaboration between municipalities, industries, farmers, researchers, and policymakers. The toolkit emphasizes the need for awareness campaigns, training programs, and financial incentives to support sustainable wastewater practices.

By applying the SmartWater Toolkit, developing countries can shift from linear wastewater treatment models to sustainable, resource-efficient practices. This initiative serves as a transformative blueprint for improving water security, enhancing agricultural productivity, and contributing to climate resilience in alignment with global sustainability goals.

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